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TOLL TEX MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT

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**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
TOLL TEX MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT
BY
KAMAL ACHARYA
(Tribhuvan University)**

Date: 2023/08/21

INTRODUCTION

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Abstract

Toll Tax Management System is a web based application that can provide all the information related to toll plazas and the passenger checks in and pays the amount, then he/she will be provided by a receipt. With this receipt he/she can leave the toll booth without waiting for any verification call.

The information would also cover registration of staff, toll plaza collection, toll plaza collection entry for vehicles, date wise report entry, Vehicle passes and passes reports b/w dates.

SYSTEM ANALYSIS

2. SYSTEM ANALYSIS

2.1 EXISTING SYSTEM:

In the existing system, current times of increasing traffic on the road, it is important to collect the toll tax in a managed and controlled process so that it doesn't result in a total unorganized jungle of traffic. It is very challenging to handle a vehicular flow by a manual system of revenue collection. Poor Management at toll Plaza may result in to great chaos and revenue loss. This would not be desired any one.

The Existing system had following Drawbacks:

- It was very time consuming
- Report were generated manually
- The Activities are often prone to errors.
- The speed of processing of data is very slow.
- The information required was not readily available.
- Lost of Papers work was there.

2.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM:

Vehicles online gate pass require less time to conduct a toll transaction. This the average service rate of a mixed toll lane is generally higher than a manual lane. Depending on the promotion of tagged vehicles in a mixed-use lane. Reduction in vehicle waiting times: An increasing in a toll lane service rate cause a decrease in the average waiting time of vehicles at the toll plaza.

Vehicle emission are reduced as vehicle speeds through the toll plaza are increased and accelerations and decelerations reduced. Reduction of toll user costs also reduces the cost of processing toll transaction. Simplified infrastructure and accounting system. Requires for less road side infrastructure than manual tollbooths.

MODULES:-

Admin

1. **Dashboard:** In this section admin can see all detail in brief like total number of staffs, Total number of vehicle category, Total number of pass, Total number of receipt, Total vehicle enter today's, yesterday's, last seven days and total vehicle pass till now in toll plaza.
2. **Staff:** In this section admin can manage staffs (add and update).
3. **Vehicle Category:** In this section admin can manage vehicle category (add and update).
4. **Pass:** In this section admin can manage pass(add and update).
5. **Receipt:** In this section admin can view receipt and take print of receipt which is make by staffs
6. **Search Pass:** In this section admin can search pass with the help of his/her pass id, owner name and vehicle number.
7. **Search Receipt:** In this section admin can search receipt with the help of his/her receipt id, owner name and vehicle number.
8. **Reports of Pass:** In this section admin can view how many pass has been made in particular periods, counts of pass and sales come from making pass.
9. **Reports of receipt:** In this section admin can view how much receipt has been made in particular periods, counts of receipt and sales come from making receipt.

Admin can also update his profile, change password and recover password.

Staffs

1. **Dashboard:** Welcome page for staff.
2. **Receipt:** In this section staff can manage receipts (add and update).
3. **Search:** In this section admin can search receipt with the help of his/her receipt id.

Staffs can also update his profile, change password and recover password.

User

User can view his transaction details like pay amount date time also.

2.3 FEASIBILITY STUDY

Preliminary investigation examine project feasibility, the likelihood the system will be useful to the organization. The main objective of the feasibility study is to test the Technical, Operational and Economical feasibility for adding new modules and debugging old running system. All system is feasible if they are unlimited resources and infinite time. There are aspects in the feasibility study portion of the preliminary investigation:

- Technical Feasibility
- Operation Feasibility
- Economical Feasibility

2.3.1. Technical Feasibility

Earlier no system existed to cater to the needs of ‘Secure Infrastructure Implementation System’. The current system developed is technically feasible. It is a web based user interface for audit workflow at NIC-CSD. Thus it provides an easy access to the users. The database’s purpose is to create, establish and maintain a workflow among various entities in order to facilitate all concerned users in their various capacities or roles. Permission to the users would be granted based on the roles specified. Therefore, it provides the technical guarantee of accuracy, reliability and security.

2.3.2. Operational Feasibility

Proposed projects are beneficial only if they can be turned out into information system. That will meet the organization’s operating requirements. Operational feasibility aspects of the project are to be taken as an important part of the project implementation.

This system is targeted to be in accordance with the above-mentioned issues. Beforehand, the management issues and user requirements have been taken into consideration. So there is no question of resistance from the users that can undermine the possible application benefits.

2.3.3. Economic Feasibility

A system can be developed technically and that will be used if installed must still be a good investment for the organization. In the economical feasibility, the development cost in creating the system is evaluated against the ultimate benefit derived from the new systems. Financial benefits must equal or exceed the costs.

The system is economically feasible. It does not require any addition hardware or software. Since the interface for this system is developed using the existing resources and technologies available at NIC, There is nominal expenditure and economical feasibility for certain.

3.SYSTEM DESIGN

INPUT DESIGN

The input design is the link between the information system and the user. It comprises the developing specification and procedures for data preparation and those steps are necessary to put transaction data in to a usable form for processing can be achieved by inspecting the computer to read data from a written or printed document or it can occur by having people keying the data directly into the system. The design of input focuses on controlling the amount of input required, controlling the errors, avoiding delay, avoiding extra steps and keeping the process simple. The input is designed in such a way so that it provides security and ease of use with retaining the privacy. Input Design considered the following things:

- What data should be given as input?
- How the data should be arranged or coded?
- The dialog to guide the operating personnel in providing input.
- Methods for preparing input validations and steps to follow when error occur.

Objectives

1. Input Design is the process of converting a user-oriented description of the input into a computer-based system. This design is important to avoid errors in the data input process and show the correct direction to the management for getting correct information from the computerized system.
2. It is achieved by creating user-friendly screens for the data entry to handle large volume of data. The goal of designing input is to make data entry easier and to be free from errors. The data entry screen is designed in such a way that all the data manipulates can be performed. It also provides record viewing facilities.
3. When the data is entered it will check for its validity. Data can be entered with the help of screens. Appropriate messages are provided as when needed so that the user will not be in

maize of instant. Thus the objective of input design is to create an input layout that is easy to follow

OUTPUT DESIGN

A quality output is one, which meets the requirements of the end user and presents the information clearly. In any system results of processing are communicated to the users and to other system through outputs. In output design it is determined how the information is to be displaced for immediate need and also the hard copy output. It is the most important and direct source information to the user. Efficient and intelligent output design improves the system's relationship to help user decision-making.

1. Designing computer output should proceed in an organized, well thought out manner; the right output must be developed while ensuring that each output element is designed so that people will find the system can use easily and effectively. When analysis design computer output, they should Identify the specific output that is needed to meet the requirements.
2. Select methods for presenting information.
3. Create document, report, or other formats that contain information produced by the system.

The output form of an information system should accomplish one or more of the following objectives.

- ❖ Convey information about past activities, current status or projections of the
- ❖ Future.
- ❖ Signal important events, opportunities, problems, or warnings.
- ❖ Trigger an action.
- ❖ Confirm an action.

3.2 DETAILED DESIGN

Table Name: Register

Fields	Data types (Constraints)
id	Int(Primary,autoincrement)
Username	Varchar(50)
Mobile	Varchar(50)
Email	Varchar(50)
Password	Varchar(50)
Gender	Varchar(50)
Address	Varchar(50)
Dob	Varchar(50)
Vehicle_Type	Varchar(50)
RegisterNumber	Varchar(50)

Table Name: tblCategory

Fields	Data types (Constraints)
id	Int(Primary,autoincrement)
Vehicle_cat	Varchar(50)
CreationDate	Timestamp

Table Name: tbladmin

Fields	Data types (Constraints)
id	Int(Primary,autoincrement)
AdminName	Varchar(50)
Username	Varchar(150)
Mobilenumber	Varchar(50)
Email	Varchar(50)
Password	Varchar(50)
AdminRegDate	Varchar(50)

Table Name: tblQueries

Fields	Data types (Constraints)
id	Int(Primary,autoincrement)
Uname	Varchar(50)
Mobile	Varchar(150)
Email	Varchar(50)
Queries	Varchar(250)

Table Name: tblpass

Fields	Data types (Constraints)
id	Int(Primary,autoincrement)
Pass_id	Varchar(50)
Vehicle_cat	Varchar(50)
VehicleName	Varchar(50)
Reg_Number	Varchar(50)
ValidityFrom	Varchar(50)
ValidityTo	Varchar(50)

AppName	Varchar(50)
AppGender	Varchar(50)
AppAge	Varchar(50)
AppAdd	Varchar(50)
PassCost	Varchar(50)

Table Name: tblreceipt

Fields	Data types (Constraints)
Id	Int(Primary,autoincrement)
Staff_id	int
Lane_Number	Varchar(150)
Receiptid	Varchar(100)
Vehicle_cat	Varchar(50)
Vehicle_Name	Varchar(50)
OwnerName	Varchar(50)
VehicleNumber	Varchar(40)
VehicleCity	Varchar(50)
Trip	Varchar(50)

Cost	Varchar(50)
CreationDate	Varchar(50)

Table Name: tblstaff

Fields	Data types (Constraints)
Id	Int(Primary,autoincrement)
Staffid	Varchar(50)
Staffname	Varchar(50)
Staffmobilenumber	Varchar(50)
Staffemail	Varchar(50)
Staffgender	Varchar(50)
Staffaddress	Varchar(50)
staffDob	Varchar(50)
staffPassword	Varchar(50)
joiningDate	Varchar(50)

Table Name: Userpass

Fields	Data types (Constraints)
Id	Int(Primary,autoincrement)
Vehiclecat	Varchar(50)
Reg_Number	Varchar(50)
App_Name	Varchar(50)
Vehiclename	Varchar(50)
Month	Varchar(50)
AppAdd	Varchar(50)
PassCost	Varchar(50)
Status	Varchar(50)

SYSTEM SPECIFICATION

1. SYSTEM SPECIFICATION

4.1 Hardware Specification:

System : Pentium IV 2.4 GHz.
Hard Disk : 40 GB.
Floppy Drive : 1.44 Mb.
Monitor : 15 VGA Colour.
Mouse : Logitech.
Ram : 512 Mb.

4.2 Software Specification:

Operating System : Windows XP or later
Database Server : MySQL 5.0
Client : Microsoft Internet Explorer
User Interface : HTML with Ajax
Code Behind : PHP

SOFTWARE DESCRIPTION

4.3 SOFTWARE DESCRIPTION

Windows

Windows is one of the most important operating systems worldwide due to its large support base. UNIX was originally developed as a multi-tasking mainframe computer operating system in the 1970s. Windows is a freely distributable version of UNIX developed primarily by Linus Torvalds at the University of Helsinki in Finland. Windows is a complete multitasking, multi-user operating system. The Windows kernel is known as a monolithic kernel as opposed to a micro-kernel, in that all the device drivers are part of the kernel. The Windows kernel is developed to use the special protected-mode features of the Intel 80x86 processors. Windows also supports networking through two primary networking protocols TCP (Transmission Control Protocol) and UUCP (Unix-To-Unix Copy Protocol). Most TCP networks use Ethernet as the physical network transport. Windows supports many popular Ethernet cards and interfaces for personal computers. Windows has many advantages as a Web server- it runs for long periods of without needing rebooting, and apache, the most popular Web server, runs much better on Windows than on the Windows operating system. Apache is automatically installed when you install most Windows distributions. Most distributions of Windows now come with support for MySQL (my Structured Query Language) and PHP (PHP: Hypertext Pre-processor) included. MySQL is a fast, easy to use Relational Database Management System (RDBMS) very popular with Web developers. PHP is a scripting language designed specifically for use on the Web.

Apache

Apache server is one of the most popular Web service applications. Apache is a powerful, flexible, HTTP/1.1 compliant web server. It is highly configurable and extensible with third-party modules. Users can further customize Apache by writing modules using the Apache module. Apache implements the following features:

- Database Management (DBM) databases for authentication that allows the user to set up password-protected pages with large numbers of authorized users, without bogging down the server.
- Customized responses to errors and problems which allows you to set up files, or even CGI scripts, which are returned by the server in response to errors and problems
- Unlimited flexible URL rewriting and aliasing meaning Apache has no fixed limit on the numbers of Aliases and Redirects which may be declared in the config files. In addition, a powerful rewriting engine can be used to solve most URL manipulation problems.
- Virtual Hosts which are often referred to as multi-homed servers. This allows the server to distinguish between requests made to different IP addresses or names (mapped to the same machine). Apache also offers dynamically configurable mass-virtual hosting.
- Apache can be configured to generate reliable piped logs, such as an error log. In addition, on most UNIX architectures, Apache can send log files to a pipe, allowing for log rotation, hit filtering, real-time splitting of multiple vhosts into separate logs, and asynchronous DNS (Domain Naming Service) resolving on the fly.

MYSQL

Structured Query Language (SQL) is the de-facto standard programming language for creating, updating and retrieving information that is stored in relational database management system. A relational database is a database divided into logical units called tables, where tables are related to one another within the database. A relational database allows large complex data to be broken down into logical, smaller, more manageable units. Tables are related to each other through a common key (data value) in a relational database. SQL is a formal programming language. Speed was the developer's main focus when SQL was being developed.

MySQL is a fast easy to use RDMS. MySQL is easier to install and use than its commercial competitors and the fact that MySQL is open source is strongly in its favor. MySQL is available via the General Public License (GPU). MySQL consists of a MySQL server, several utility programs that assist the administration of the MySQL databases. MySQL's main advantages include the following:

- It is pre-packaged with most Linux distributions
- It's quite easy to use: you can interact with a MySQL database using a few simple statements from the SQL language.
- It's very fast: MySQL's developers' main goal was speed; consequently the software was designed from the beginning with speed in mind.
- It's free via the GNU General Public License.

PHP

PHP is a scripting language designed specifically for use on the Web. PHP is a server-side scripting language which was developed for dynamic Web sites and applications. It is an embedded scripting language, which means that PHP code is embedded in HTML code. PHP scripts can parse data submitted by HTML forms, communicate with databases, and make complex calculations on the fly. PHP is very fast because the freely available source code is compiled into the Apache Web server. A PHP script is executed as part of the Web server process and requires no forking, often a criticism of Common Gateway Interface (CGI) scripts. PHP interacts with the database by invoking SQL commands, and displays the results in dynamically generated Web pages. PHP provides the application part and MYSQL provides the database part of a Web database application. PHP is used to move data into and out of the MYSQL database. PHP is also suitable for more complicated tasks such as parsing and verifying data that the user has entered into an HTML form. PHP's advantages include the following:

It's free via the GNU General Public License (GPL).

It's fast due to the fact that it's embedded into the HTML code.

It's designed to support databases including functionality designed to interact with specific databases. It negates the need for the user to need to know the technical details required to communicate with a database.

It's quite easy to use in that it only contains elements of a programming language needed to interact with a database and to generate dynamic web-pages.

SYSTEM TESTING

5 SYSTEM TESTING

The purpose of testing is to discover errors. Testing is the process of trying to discover every conceivable fault or weakness in a work product. It provides a way to check the functionality of components, sub-assemblies, assemblies and/or a finished product. It is the process of exercising software with the intent of ensuring that the software system meets its requirements and user expectations and does not fail in an unacceptable manner. There are various types of test. Each test type addresses a specific testing requirement.

TYPES OF TESTS

UNIT TESTING

Unit testing involves the design of test cases that validate that the internal program logic is functioning properly, and that program inputs produce valid outputs. All decision branches and internal code flow should be validated. It is the testing of individual software units of the application. It is done after the completion of an individual unit before integration. This is a structural testing, that relies on knowledge of its construction and is invasive. Unit tests perform basic tests at component level and test a specific business process, application, and/or system configuration. Unit tests ensure that each unique path of a business process performs accurately to the documented specifications and contains clearly defined inputs and expected results.

INTEGRATION TESTING

Integration tests are designed to test integrated software components to determine if they actually run as one program. Testing is event driven and is more concerned with the basic outcome of screens or fields. Integration tests demonstrate that although the components were individually satisfactory, as shown by successfully unit testing, the combination of components is correct and consistent. Integration testing is specifically aimed at exposing the problems that arise from the combination of components.

Functional test

Functional tests provide systematic demonstrations that functions tested are available as specified by the business and technical requirements, system documentation, and user manuals.

Functional testing is centered on the following items:

Valid Input : identified classes of valid input must be accepted.

Invalid Input : identified classes of invalid input must be rejected.

Functions : identified functions must be exercised.

Output : identified classes of application outputs must be exercised.

Systems/Procedures: interfacing systems or procedures must be invoked.

Organization and preparation of functional tests is focused on requirements, key functions, or special test cases. In addition, systematic coverage pertaining to identify Business process flows; data fields, predefined processes, and successive processes must be considered for testing. Before functional testing is complete, additional tests are identified and the effective value of current tests is determined.

SYSTEM TESTING

System testing ensures that the entire integrated software system meets requirements. It tests a configuration to ensure known and predictable results. An example of system testing is the configuration oriented system integration test. System testing is based on process descriptions and flows, emphasizing pre-driven process links and integration points.

WHITE BOX TESTING

White Box Testing is a testing in which in which the software tester has knowledge of the inner workings, structure and language of the software, or at least its purpose. It is purpose. It is used to test areas that cannot be reached from a black box level.

BLACK BOX TESTING

Black Box Testing is testing the software without any knowledge of the inner workings, structure or language of the module being tested. Black box tests, as most other kinds of tests, must be written from a definitive source document, such as specification or requirements document, such as specification or requirements document. It is a testing in which the software under test is treated, as a black box .you cannot “see” into it. The test provides inputs and responds to outputs without considering how the software works.

ACCEPTANCE TESTING

User Acceptance Testing is a critical phase of any project and requires significant participation by the end user. It also ensures that the system meets the functional requirements.

Test Results: All the test cases mentioned above passed successfully. No defects encountered.

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

6. SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

After the system is implemented and Conversion is completed, a review of the personal is good. They are Satisfied with this Software facility. Less man power, provide information timely. Save data entry and duplication work. Timing and also resources allocation for data entry, it fills the gap between data entry. Provide the lock system and password protection so it is reliable.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

7.1 CONCLUSION

The project titled as **Toll Tax Management System** was deeply studied and analyzed to design the code and implement. It was done under the guidance of the experienced project guide. All the current requirements and possibilities have been taken care during the project time.

Toll Tax management system is used for daily operations in any organization to maintain or access toll related information for internal administration purposes.

7.2 FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

This System being web-based and an undertaking of Cyber Security Division, needs to be thoroughly tested to find out any security gaps. A console for the data centre may be made available to allow the personnel to monitor on the sites which were cleared for hosting during a particular period. Moreover, it is just a beginning; further the system may be utilized in various other types of auditing operation viz. Network auditing or similar process/workflow based applications.

APPENDIX

9.1 SOURCE CODE

Index.php

```
<?php
session_start();
error_reporting(0);
include('includes/dbconnection.php');

if(isset($_POST['login']))
{
    $semail=$_POST['semail'];
    $password=md5($_POST['password']);

    $query=mysqli_query($con,"select ID from tblstaff where StaffEmail='$semail' &&
StaffPassword='$password'");

    $ret=mysqli_fetch_array($query);

    if($ret>0){
        $_SESSION['ttmssid']=$ret['ID'];
        header('location:dashboard.php');
    }
    else{
        $msg="Invalid Details.";
    }
}

?>

<!DOCTYPE HTML>

<html>

<head>
```

```
<title>Toll Tax Management System || Login Page</title>
```

```
<script type="application/x-javascript"> addEventListener("load", function() { setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0);  
, false); function hideURLbar(){ window.scrollTo(0,1); } </script>
```

```
<!-- Bootstrap Core CSS -->
```

```
<link href="css/bootstrap.min.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
```

```
<!-- Custom CSS -->
```

```
<link href="css/style.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />
```

```
<link href="css/font-awesome.css" rel="stylesheet">
```

```
<!-- jQuery -->
```

```
<script src="js/jquery.min.js"></script>
```

```
<!--webfonts-->
```

```
<link href='http://fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Roboto:400,100,300,500,700,900' rel='stylesheet'  
type='text/css'>
```

```
<!--//webfonts-->
```

```
<!-- Bootstrap Core JavaScript -->
```

```
<script src="js/bootstrap.min.js"></script>
```

```
</head>
```

```
<body id="login">
```

```
<div class="login-logo">
```

```
<a href="index.php"><strong style="color: black">Toll Tax Management System</strong></a>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<h2 class="form-heading">login</h2>
```

```
<div class="app-cam">
```

```
<form method="post">
```

```
<p style="font-size:16px; color:red" align="center"> <?php if($msg){
```

```

    echo $msg;

} ?> </p>

<input type="text" class="text" name="semail" placeholder="Staff Email" required="true">

        <input type="password" name="password" class="text" placeholder="Password"
required="true">

        <div class="submit"><input type="submit" value="Login" name="login"></div>

        <ul class="new">

                <li class="new_left"><p><a href="forgot-password.php">Forgot Password
?</a></p></li>

                <li class="new_right"><p><a href=" ../index.php">Back to Home</a></p></li>

                </li>

                <div class="clearfix"></div>

        </ul>

    </form>

</div>

<?php include_once('includes/footer.php');?>

</body>

</html>

```

Add Receipt.Php

```

<?php
session_start();
error_reporting(0);
include('includes/dbconnection.php');
if (strlen($_SESSION['tmssid']==0)) {

```

```

header('location:logout.php');

} else{

    if(isset($_POST['submit']))

    {

        $sid=$_SESSION['tmsid'];

        $catname=$_POST['catname'];

        $lanename=$_POST['lanename'];

        $vname=$_POST['vname'];

        $oname=$_POST['oname'];

        $vehno=$_POST['vehno'];

        $evcity=$_POST['evcity'];

        $strip=$_POST['trip'];

        $cost=$_POST['cost'];

        $receiptid = mt_rand(100000000, 999999999);

        $query=mysqli_query($con, "insert into
tblreceipt(Staffid,Receiptid,VehicleCat,LaneNumber,VehicleName,OwnerName,VehicleNumber,
EnterVehiclecity,Trip,Cost)
value('$sid', '$receiptid', '$catname', '$lanename', '$vname', '$oname', '$vehno', '$evcity', '$strip', '$cost
')");

        if ($query) {

            echo '<script>alert("Receipt has been created.")</script>';

            echo "<script>>window.location.href='add-receipt.php'</script>";

        }

        else

        {

```

```

        echo '<script>alert("Something Went Wrong. Please try again")</script>';
    }

}

?>

<!DOCTYPE HTML>

<html>

<head>

<title>Toll Tax Management System || Add Receipt</title>

<script type="application/x-javascript"> addEventListener("load", function() {
setTimeout(hideURLbar, 0); }, false); function hideURLbar(){ window.scrollTo(0,1); } </script>

<!-- Bootstrap Core CSS -->

<link href="css/bootstrap.min.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />

<!-- Custom CSS -->

<link href="css/style.css" rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' />

<link href="css/font-awesome.css" rel="stylesheet">

<!-- jQuery -->

<script src="js/jquery.min.js"></script>

<!--webfonts-->

<link href='http://fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Roboto:400,100,300,500,700,900'
rel='stylesheet' type='text/css'>

<!--//webfonts-->

<!-- Bootstrap Core JavaScript -->

<script src="js/bootstrap.min.js"></script>

```

```

</head>
<body>
<div id="wrapper">
  <!-- Navigation -->
  <?php include_once('includes/sidebar.php');?>
  <?php include_once('includes/header.php');?>
  <div id="page-wrapper">
    <div class="col-md-12 graphs">
      <div class="xs">
        <h3>Add Receipt</h3>
        <div class="well1 white">
          <form class="form-floating ng-pristine ng-invalid ng-invalid-required ng-valid-email ng-
valid-url ng-valid-pattern" method="post">
            <p style="font-size:16px; color:red" align="center"> <?php if($msg){
echo $msg;
} ?> </p>
            <fieldset>
              <div class="form-group">
                <label class="control-label">Vehicle Category</label>
                <select type="text" class="form-control1 ng-invalid ng-invalid-required ng-touched"
required="true" id="catname" name="catname" value="">
                  <option value="">Choose Category</option>
                  <?php $query=mysqli_query($con,"select * from tblcategory");
                  while($row=mysqli_fetch_array($query))
                  {

```

```

?>
    <option value="<?php echo $row['VehicleCat'];?>"><?php echo
$row['VehicleCat'];?></option>
    <?php } ?>
</select>
</div>
<div class="form-group">
    <label class="control-label">Name of lane</label>
    <select type="text" class="form-control1 ng-invalid ng-invalid-required ng-touched"
required="true" id="lanename" name="lanename" value="">
        <option value="">Choose Lane Number</option>
        <option value="Lane1">Lane Number 1</option>
        <option value="Lane2">Lane Number 2</option>
        <option value="Lane3">Lane Number 3</option>
        <option value="Lane4">Lane Number 4</option>
    </select>
</div>
<div class="form-group">
    <label class="control-label">Vehicle Name</label>
    <input type="text" class="form-control1 ng-invalid ng-invalid-required ng-touched"
required="true" id="vname" name="vname" value="">
</div>
<div class="form-group">
    <label class="control-label">Owner Name</label>
    <input type="text" class="form-control1 ng-invalid ng-invalid-required ng-touched"
required="true" id="oname" name="oname" value="">
</div>

```

```
<div class="form-group">
  <label class="control-label">Vehicle Number</label>
  <input type="text" class="form-control1 ng-invalid ng-invalid-required ng-touched"
required="true" id="vehno" name="vehno" value="">
</div>
```

```
<div class="form-group">
  <label class="control-label">Enter Vehicle City</label>
  <input type="text" class="form-control1 ng-invalid ng-invalid-required ng-touched"
required="true" id="evcity" name="evcity" value="">
</div>
```

```
<div class="form-group">
  <label class="control-label">Trip</label>
  <select type="text" class="form-control1 ng-invalid ng-invalid-required ng-touched"
required="true" id="trip" name="trip" value="">
    <option value="">Choose Trip</option>
    <option value="One Way Trip">One Way Trip</option>
    <option value="Two Way Trip">Two Way Trip</option>
  </select>
</div>
```

```
<div class="form-group">
  <label class="control-label">Cost</label>
  <input type="text" class="form-control1 ng-invalid ng-invalid-required ng-touched"
required="true" id="cost" name="cost" value="">
</div>
```

```
<div class="form-group">
    <p style="text-align: center;"> <button type="submit" name="submit" class="btn btn-
primary">Add</button></p>

</div>

</fieldset>

</form>

</div>

</div>

<?php include_once('includes/footer.php');?>

</div>

</div>

<!-- /#page-wrapper -->

</div>

<!-- /#wrapper -->

<!-- Nav CSS -->

<link href="css/custom.css" rel="stylesheet">

<!-- Metis Menu Plugin JavaScript -->

<script src="js/metisMenu.min.js"></script>

<script src="js/custom.js"></script>

</body>

</html>

<?php } ?>
```

SCREEN SHOTS

Home Page

Admin Login

Dashboard

The dashboard features a green header with the 'TTMS' logo and a user profile icon. A dark sidebar on the left contains a menu with the following items: Dashboard, Staff, Vehicle Category, Pass, Details of Receipts, Search Pass, Search Receipt, Reports of Pass, and Reports of Receipt. The main content area displays eight summary cards in a 2x4 grid:

- Total Staffs:** 3
- Total Vehicle Category:** 4
- Total Pass:** 6
- Total Receipt:** 2
- Today's Number of Vehicles:** 0
- Yesterdays Number of Vehicles:** 0
- Last 7 Days Number of Vehicles:** 0
- Total vehicles Enter Till Date:** 2

At the bottom center, the text 'Toll Tax Management System @ 2019' is displayed.

Add Staff

The 'Add Staff' page has a green header with 'TTMS' and a user profile icon. The sidebar menu is identical to the dashboard but highlights 'Add Staff'. The main form area contains the following fields:

- Staff Name
- Staff Mobile Number
- Staff Email Address
- Staff Password
- Staff Gender: Female Male Other
- Staff Address
- Staff DOB (format: dd-mm-yyyy)

An 'Add' button is located at the bottom right of the form.

Manage Staff

TTMS

Manage Staff

S.NO	Staff ID	Staff Name	Action
1	207706148	John Shah	Edit
2	569377192	Sneha Kumari	Edit
3	590935860	Sanju Mishra	Edit

Update Staff Information

TTMS

Update Staff Information

Staff Name
John Shah

Staff ID
207706148

Staff Mobile Number
7789787877

Staff Email Address
shah@gmail.com

Staff Gender: Male Female

Staff Address
X block jhangirpuri allahabad

Staff DOB
09-05-1980

Staff Joining Date
2019-08-22 17:56:49

[Update](#)

Add Vehicle Category

TTMS

Add Category

Vehicle Category

[Add](#)

Toll Tax Management System @ 2019

- Dashboard
- Staff
- Vehicle Category
 - Add Category
 - Manage Category
- Pass
- Details of Receipts
- Search Pass
- Search Receipt
- Reports of Pass
- Reports of Receipt

Manage Category

TTMS

Manage Category

S.NO	Vehicle Category Name	Date of Creation	Action
1	Four Wheeler	2019-08-22 18:21:20	Edit
2	Six Wheeler	2019-08-22 18:21:58	Edit
3	Two Wheeler	2019-08-22 18:22:14	Edit
4	Three Wheeler	2019-08-22 18:22:24	Edit

Toll Tax Management System @ 2019

- Dashboard
- Staff
- Vehicle Category
 - Add Category
 - Manage Category
- Pass
- Details of Receipts
- Search Pass
- Search Receipt
- Reports of Pass
- Reports of Receipt

Update Category

TTMS

Update Category

Vehicle Category

Four Wheeler

Add

Add New Pass

TTMS

Add New Pass

Vehicle Category

Choose Category

Vehicle Name

Vehicle Reg Number

Validity From

dd-mm-yyyy

Validity To

dd-mm-yyyy

Name of Applicant

Age of Applicant

Applicant Gender: Female Male

Address of Applicant

Cost of Pass

Add

Manage Pass

TTMS

Dashboard

Staff

Vehicle Category

Pass

 Add New Pass

 Manage New Pass

Details of Receipts

Search Pass

Search Receipt

Reports of Pass

Reports of Receipt

View Pass

S.NO	Pass ID	Name of Applicant	Date of Creation	Action
1	356435118	Raghav	2019-08-28 10:47:26	View
2	356435112	Chitranjan Dubey	2019-08-28 10:51:44	View
3	356435113	Gaurav	2019-08-28 11:06:10	View
4	356435116	Renu Kumari	2019-08-28 11:08:24	View
5	356435119	Veena Pathak	2019-08-28 11:10:24	View
6	936497424	Veena Pathak	2019-08-30 11:21:17	View

Print Pass

TTMS

Dashboard

Staff

Vehicle Category

Pass

Details of Receipts

Search Pass

Search Receipt

Reports of Pass

Reports of Receipt

View Pass

Vehicle Category	Four Wheeler
Pass ID	356435118
Vehicle Name	Maruty
Vehicle Reg Number	Del 4567
Validity From	2019-08-28
Validity To	2019-09-28
Name of Applicant	Raghav
Age of Applicant	36
Gender of Applicant	Male
Address of Applicant	F-1226 grater Kailash Delhi
Cost of Pass	560

View Receipt

TTMS

- Dashboard
- Staff
- Vehicle Category
- Pass
- Details of Receipts
- Search Pass
- Search Receipt
- Reports of Pass
- Reports of Receipt

View Receipt

S.NO	Receipt ID	Owner Name	Date of Creation	Action
1	724436932	Nelesh Gupta	2019-08-28 17:18:31	View Details
2	177051826	John Fernadesh	2019-08-29 10:55:55	View Details

Print Receipt

TTMS

- Dashboard
- Staff
- Vehicle Category
- Pass
- Details of Receipts
- Search Pass
- Search Receipt
- Reports of Pass
- Reports of Receipt

View Receipt

Lane Number	Lane2
Receipt ID	724436932
Vehicle Category	Four Wheeler
Vehicle Name	Car
Owner Name	Nelesh Gupta
Vehicle Reg Number	Del-6789
Vehicle Enter City	Chandigarh
Trip	Two Way Trip
Cost	680
Date of Receipt Generate	2019-08-28 17:18:31

Search Pass

TTMS

Search Pass

Search by Pass ID / Applicant Name / Vehicle Reg Number

Search

Result against "356435118" keyword

S.NO	Pass ID	Name of Applicant	Vehicle Reg. Number	Date of Creation	Action
1	356435118	Raghav	Del 4567	2019-08-28 10:47:26	View

Search Receipt

TTMS

Search Receipt

Search by Receipt Number/ Vehicle Number / Owner Name

Search

Result against "724436932" keyword

S.NO	Receipt ID	Owner Name	vehicle Reg. Number	Date of Creation	Action
1	724436932	Nelesh Gupta	Del-6789	2019-08-28 17:18:31	View Details

Staff Login

Add Receipt

User Login

Add New Pass

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